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ASSESSMENT OF INTERNS KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND SKILL ON CARDIOPULMONARY RESUSCITATION (CPR) IN A NIGERIAN POPULATION

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ABSTRACT

Developing nations such as Nigeria have fragile healthcare system characterized with dilapidated health facilities and shortage of medical personnel which predisposes the population to conditions

of sudden death where CPR will be a vital skill. Medical Interns in these areas are thus uniquely positioned as frontline responders to emergencies. The Objectives of the Study therefore include; assessing the knowledge of interns on CPR, to assess the skills of interns on CPR and to assess the attitude of interns to performing CPR at any time. A Cross-sectional study was carried out among 126 interns in Obafemi Awolowo Teaching Hospital Ife, a federal teaching hospital in Nigeria. The respondents were mainly female (76.2%). They demonstrated both good knowledge and attitude in CPR but there was gap between knowledge/attitude and skill of CPR with only 47.6% having good skill. Moderate positive correlation ($r=0.517$, $p<0.001$) exist between knowledge and skill, weak positive correlation ($r=0.376$, $p < 0.01$) exist between knowledge and attitude and very weak correlation ($r=0.155$, $p < 0.01$) between attitude and skill. Interns with previous CPR training scored significantly higher in both knowledge ($p < 0.001$), practice ($p < 0.001$) and attitude ($p < 0.001$) than those who had not. Nursing interns performed better than other departments across all the questions ($p=0.001$). Our study showed that the interns have a good attitude and knowledge in CPR. Their practical skills however, need improvement. We therefore highly recommended that medical programs should include more frequent "hands-on" CPR simulation drills.

KEYWORDS: Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation, Medical Intern, Emergency

INTRODUCTION

CPR is a first medical procedure that is given to somebody whose heart has stopped beating or who has cardiac arrest(1). CPR is a vital tool in hospital and out of hospital practice for prevention of sudden death, prevention of worsening conditions of death and promotion of recovery (2) (3). According to American Heart Association (AHA), CPR is defined as the provision of rescue breaths and chest compressions to help restore blood circulation and breathing in a person who has stopped breathing or whose heart has stopped breathing (2). CPR is a first line emergency effort aimed at restoration of oxygenation to the body especially the brain and other vital organs for cardiac arrest patient.

Many studies showed that there is dearth in skill of CPR among the healthcare professionals (4)(5). A Research study (6) stated that CPR should be started within 2 minutes of arrest to ensure best chance of survival. Studies (7) (8), stressed that every minute that passes, without BLS for cardiac arrest patient, increases the death rate by 7-10%. More than 60% of patients can survive with early resuscitation within 01 minute (9). CPR is also vital in survival of patients/individuals emergencies such as stroke, trauma, respiratory arrest, drowning, and air way obstruction. It is a component of basic life support.

Developing nations such as Nigeria, have fragile healthcare system characterized with dilapidated/outdated health facilities, shortage of medical personnel, poor regulation, and poor remuneration of health workers and others such as bad roads, insecurities, inflation and current food shortage(10). These are risk factors for cardiac arrest and cardiac related diseases, stroke, diabetes, and respiratory diseases which invariably has the potential of increasing the incidence of sudden death and the need for CPR. Due to shortage of man power/ experienced hands in developing countries, interns appear to be easy reach in cases of emergencies.

Interns are medical graduates transitioning towards independent practice. They are uniquely positioned as frontline responders to emergencies in the hospitals. They are viewed also as pillars of medical leadership in their communities-particularly in developing nations and resource limited areas where they may be the only trained professional available. Equipping them with the correct approach to CPR fosters competence, confidence, and sense of professional duty necessary for

immediate action. The result of their assessment helps in identifying critical gaps and refinement of their training program.

CPR is not restricted only to health workers; educating the interns is also indirect ways of reaching the public. There appear to be no much significant work done in assessing interns' knowledge, attitude and skill on CPR in this region. Due to the importance of CPR and BLS (Basic Life Support) skills in the prevention of sudden death in emergency situation (2)(3), some countries have made it mandatory for their healthcare professionals (11). Furthermore, Cardiopulmonary resuscitation and BLS certification is valid only for 2 years which therefore call for continuous and regular recertification among health care professionals whose work exposes them to more frequent scenarios of sudden death. The aim of the study is thus to assess interns' skills, knowledge and attitude towards CPR.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Cardiopulmonary resuscitation has been proven to be highly effective in salvaging many cases of sudden death that can be given virtually anywhere by trained individual both inside and outside the hospital (2) (3). Many researchers have reported that timely administering of CPR increases the chance of survival of cardiac arrest (9)(6)(7). Risk factors of sudden death are numerous in developing countries like Nigeria (10). These include diabetes, obesity, hypertension, respiratory disorders, and trauma etcetera. The burdens of sudden death are devastating ranging from loss of man power, disunity in family, poverty, unemployment, etcetera. Cardiopulmonary resuscitation skills, which have been acclaimed as effective in prevention of sudden death, are indispensable. Acquisition of such skills needs to be given high importance. Nigeria also is bewildered with many problems such as shortage of healthcare professionals due to continuous massive exodus of medical workers in search of greener pastures. (12)

Internship is the immediate post-graduation program for most of the medical professionals, mostly lasting for a year, for interns to learn and achieve confidence in practical professional skills. In this era of shortage of manpower, interns tend to be more visible. Assessing and equipping them adequately on CPR skills and BLS will enhance the prevention of sudden death.

CPR is a medical emergency procedure that involves chest compressions with rescue breaths to maintain heart and lungs functions thereby ensuring blood circulation and breathing with the aim of ensuring supply of oxygen to vital tissues of the body and the brain (1)(14)(15). It can be applied to cardiac arrest, near drowning or trauma victim. CPR can be done on adult, children and neonate (1)(15) Steps of administering CPR are the same irrespective of age of the individual with little variations with children (1)(15).The steps include:

- 1) Assess the location for your own safety before going close to the victim.
- 2) Call for help if you noticed someone in need of CPR before starting the CPR. If you are more than one, the other person should call for help while you start the CPR.
- 3) Move the patient to a better position and out of immediate danger. Check the patient ABC (airway, breathing and circulation).
- 4) Start chest compressions
- 5) Give rescue breaths at the appropriate count of chest compression.
- 6) Continue the CPR until the patient start showing sign of regaining consciousness or you are physically unable to continue.

In adults, compression is done with the help of one hand on the center of the person's chest, just above the nipple line. Place the other hand on the top of the first hand with the fingers interlaced.

The chest is compressed to the depth of 2-3 inches. In child of 1-8 years, this method is the same but the chest is compressed to 1/3 of the chest cavity. But for infant CPR (0-12 months), place your thumb side by side on the centre of the infant's chest, just above the nipple line. Compression is done to the depth of 1/4 of the chest cavity.

Many challenges of CPR have been reported (1)(15). These include risk of infection (contact with body fluid such as blood and saliva), not being able to focus probably because of distraction from the environment, fatigue, extreme weather, limited space or emotional challenges where the person could not withstand losing someone or a loved one is involved. Not having CPR mask, easy access to help or automated external defibrillator (AED) to augment CPR are also some of the challenges. Adequate training and retraining are keys to overcoming the challenges (14)(16).

Study (3) on assessment of knowledge, attitude and skills of 256 healthcare workers on CPR in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria, revealed that 55.5% had good knowledge of CPR while 44.5% had poor knowledge. It also showed that 60.5% had positive attitude and 56.2% had adequate skills as against 43.8% with inadequate skill. There was positive relationship between health workers knowledge and attitude with level of skills. Queeneth Kalu, Toresa, Ogban et al (17) in their work on proportion of healthcare workers with BLS training as well as the number available for such training in public health facilities in Cross River state Nigeria, studied 205 healthcare facilities within 18 local government area (LGA). Sixteen (16) healthcare facilities had staff trained on BLS indicating an average of 0.37 trained staff per facility. While 9.3% of the health facilities had at least a doctor and nurse available for BLS training.

Majority of healthcare practitioners that were not trained in BLS were community health officers and community health extension workers. They concluded that there is gross lack of BLS trained healthcare workers in the area.

A study (5) on knowledge, attitude and practice of CPR among nurses in Babcock University Teaching Hospital in Ogun state Nigeria, found that 74.9% of nurses had good knowledge of CPR, 65.2% had practiced CPR and 56.3% had negative attitude towards CPR. They concluded that the majority of the nurses have good knowledge of CPR but only few had positive attitude towards CPR practice.

Also, a study (14) in India by Dheeraji, Mahantra and Manos et al on assessment of basic life support knowledge among allied health professionals indicated that majority of the respondent demonstrated strong BLS knowledge with correct responses ranging from 51% to 90% while a study (4) conducted in Karach; among 101 final year student of Doctor of Physical Therapy indicated approximately 69.3% had the correct knowledge of CPR and 85% were willing to perform CPR on anyone, if necessary. All the participants were aware of CPR but 49.5% only believed their knowledge was adequate. Half of the students had previously taken CPR training course, yet only 27.7% had done so within the past year.

In Saudia Arabia, Abdalelah, Ahmed, Ali et al, 2022 (16) conducted an evidence based assessment of CPR knowledge among 416 healthcare providers. They found that 41.8% were BLS certified, and 38.5% were double certified in BLS and ACLS. The study showed that 62% had average knowledge, 22% had poor knowledge and 16% had good knowledge. They found that being certified in life support courses was not associated with a higher level of knowledge, though this was contrary to findings of other authors ,(17) (16) They concluded that the overall knowledge of health workers is below expectation

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A Cross-sectional approach was adopted for this study among 126 interns in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital Complex Ife, in Nigeria. Yaro Yamani sampling method was used to calculate appropriate sample size of 119 interns. Yaro Yamani 1967 (18) simplified formula:

$$n = N / [(1 + N(e)^2)]$$

Where;

n = sample size, N = total number of interns, E = level of precision = 0- 05.

$$n = 170 / [1 + 170(0.05)^2] = 119.$$

Convenience sampling technique was used to select willing interns into the study. Medicine and surgery with dentistry interns were excluded from the study since their undergraduate training were slightly different in the country. Already validated questionnaire from published literature was adopted for the study. The questionnaires were distributed and returned through WhatsApp messaging application using Google form. The result was analyzed using Excel in line with the objectives of the study. Ethical approval was obtained from the teaching hospital ethical committee and the questionnaire preparation and administration was done in line with ethical principles to ensure responder's anonymity.

RESULT

The questions used to test the knowledge, attitude and skills of the interns on CPR is presented in table 1 below. They were scored using scale of three levels - Good, Fair, and Poor. Seven questions were used to test for knowledge, 9 questions for attitude and 5 questions were used to test for skill of the interns in CPR.

Table 1: Questions used to test the Knowledge, Attitude and Skills of the Interns on CPR

Category	Questionnaire Item (Question)
Knowledge (Theory & Guidelines)	CPR consists of the use of chest compressions and artificial ventilation to maintain circulatory flow and oxygenation during cardiac arrest.
	Cardio-pulmonary Resuscitation (CPR) is NOT most effective when started immediately after the patient collapse.
	The best way to open the airway prior to giving mouth to-mouth ventilation is to tilt the head back and lift the chin up.
	The chest compression landmark on adult is at the center of the chest just at the ziphoid.

Category	Questionnaire Item (Question)
	Chest compressions should be performed on an infant with two fingers of one hand while doing CPR.
	The steps of CPR in the correct sequence is compression, maintain a patent airway and artificial breathing.
	The recommended compression to ventilation ratio is 30:2.
Attitude (Professional Mindset & Willingness)	I think that CPR training course should be mandatory for all healthcare workers.
	I think Mouth to mouth ventilation should not be performed on opposite sex during CPR.
	I feel Doctors only should be responsible for initiating CPR.
	CPR should not be practice, if necessary, equipment is not easily found.
	I would consider it my duty to intervene in a situation requiring CPR.
	I would see CPR as a chance to help.
	I am willing to provide CPR to patients if the need arises.
	If I have the opportunity, I would like to avoid CPR.
	I do CPR to patient only in hospital environment.

Category	Questionnaire Item (Question)
Skill / Practice (Self-Reported Application)	I can perform CPR technique on a patient very efficiently.
	I do not need to check for patient pulse rate before commencing CPR.
	I pinch patient nostril before giving mouth to mouth ventilation.
	I use the same procedure to administer CPR to children and adult.
	I ensure person in cardiac emergency is laid supine on a relatively hard surface before commencing CPR.

Demographic data were obtained (figure 1, figure 2, and figure 3). The respondents were mainly female having 76.2% while the male constituted 23.8%. This is represented in a pie chart in figure 1. The respondents' age distributions fall in the range of 18 years to 33 years with 18-25 years constituting 46% and 26-33 years representing 50% of the respondents. This is represented in figure 2. Distributions of the respondents, based on their departments, were as follows: Laboratory sciences were 37 interns, Nursing 35 interns, Radiography 22 interns, pharmacy 15 interns, Dietetics 5 interns, and Dental therapist 5 interns. This is represented in figure 3.

Figure 1: Gender distribution of respondents.

Figure 2: Age distribution.

Figure 3: Distribution of respondent based on their departments.

Among the interns, 62.7% demonstrated good knowledge of CPR, with mean score of 5.60 ± 1.42 . Good attitude to CPR was also seen among the interns with 71.4% demonstrating good attitude with mean score of 7.87 ± 1.51 . Although good level of skill was reported by the interns, 47.6% of the interns reported good skill with mean score of $3.17 \pm 1, 33$; there was gap between knowledge /attitude and skill to practice CPR. These were presented in figure 4, 5, and 6.

Figure 4: Knowledge Score distribution of the respondents.

Figure 5: Attitude distribution of the respondents.

Figure 6: Skill distribution of the interns.

Inferential statistics were calculated to determine how the three areas of study affect one another. Pearson correlation was used to determine these relationships. Knowledge of intern on CPR was shown to correlate with skill significantly with $r=0.517$, $p < 0.01$. This indicates that interns with

good theoretical knowledge are significantly more likely to have better practical skill. Weak positive correlation was seen between knowledge of CPR and attitude to CPR, $r = 0.376$, $p < 0.01$. This shows that interns with poor knowledge are not necessarily more likely to show poor attitude to performing CPR. Very weak correlation was seen between attitude to CPR and skill to practice CPR, $r=0.155$, $p < 0.01$ indicating that positive attitude to CPR does not necessarily translate to being skillful in performing CPR.

T-test was used to determine if gender or previous training plays significant role in Interns approach to CPR. There was no significance difference seen between male and female genders but Interns with previous training during their undergraduate training scored significantly higher in knowledge ($p=0.001$), attitude ($p < 0.001$) and skill ($p < 0.001$) than those that do not have previous knowledge.

ANOVA test was used to compare performance among the departments. To ensure statistical reliability, the department with fewer than 10 respondents (Dietetics and Dental therapy were grouped together into "Other Specialised Department". There is a significant difference in knowledge across departments. Nursing Interns had the highest knowledge mean score (6.29 ± 1.02). Post-hoc result (Tukey HSD) shows significant difference between Nursing and Laboratory sciences ($p=0.0125$). This implies that Nursing Interns significantly outperformed Laboratory science Interns in theoretical CPR steps. The "Other Specialized" group (Dietetics and Dental therapy) showed lower attitude to CPR (mean score 6.69 ± 2.06) compared to the rest of the departments which have positive attitude. Post-hoc result showed that the attitude of Nursing and Laboratory Sciences interns were significantly more positive than that of the Other Specialized group ($p=0.022$). Nursing Interns scored significantly higher than every other department in CPR skills (Mean score 4.00 ± 0.94 , $p < 0.05$ in all pairings). Pharmacy (2.60 ± 1.58) and "Other Specialized" (2.62 ± 1.39) Interns reported a low possession of skills in CPR. All tests passed Levene's Test for Homogeneity of variance ($p > 0.05$) meaning the variation within the groups was consistent enough for ANOVA to be valid.

DISCUSSION

Our study showed that among the interns, 62.7% demonstrated good knowledge of CPR. This is similar to findings of some studies done to evaluate Interns' knowledge of CPR. Ogundele study (3) on assessment of knowledge, attitude and skills of 256 healthcare workers on CPR in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria, revealed that 55.5% has good knowledge of CPR. Another study (5) on knowledge, attitude and practice of CPR among 135 nurses in Babcock University Teaching Hospital in Ogun state Nigeria, also found that 74.9% of nurses had good knowledge of CPR. Study (14) in India by Dheeraji, Mahantra and Manos et al on assessment of basic life support knowledge among allied health professionals indicated that majority of the respondent demonstrated strong BLS knowledge with correct responses ranging from 51% to 90%. Study (4) conducted in Karach; among 101 final year student of Doctor of Physical Therapy indicated approximately 69.3% had adequate knowledge of CPR. These similarities are expected as Interns are medical graduates being trained to assist or manage in healthcare services delivery, as CPR probably forms significant portion of their curriculum.

This study is however different from findings of a study done in Saudia Arabia by Arabia, Abdalelah, Ahmed, Ali et al, 2022 (16) on evidence based assessment of CPR knowledge among 416 healthcare providers. Their study showed that 62% had average knowledge, 22% had poor knowledge and 16% had good knowledge. They concluded that the overall knowledge of health workers is below expectation. This, probably, may be due to curriculum difference.

On attitude of medical Interns to CPR, our study found that 71.4% of interns reported good attitude. Ogundele (3) in their study found that 60.5% of their study respondent had positive attitude which is similar to our study. A study (5) found a contrary result with 44.7% of their respondent indicating negative attitude.

CPR is a service that in most cases are done outside of one's work schedule and not remunerated. Manner of encouragement from the environment may have effect. Our study found good level of skill by Interns (47.6%). Ogundele (3) in their study reported adequate skill among their respondent (56.2%). Another similar study done in Karachi (4) stated that 85% of their respondents showed evidence of CPR skill.

Knowledge, attitude and skill are different thing; each affects individual disposition and approach to CPR. Presence of good knowledge with poor attitude may not be enough encouragement to administer CPR. Same applies to CPR practical skill. On how knowledge, attitude and skill affect each other with respect to intern's disposition to administer CPR, our study showed that interns with good knowledge are significantly more likely to have better practical skill ($p < 0.01$). Weak positive relationship was however seen between knowledge of CPR and attitude to CPR. Our study further indicated that positive attitude to CPR does not necessarily translate to being good skill wise in performing CPR ($P < 0.01$). Most of the study reviewed could not make input on these areas probably due to nature of participants or study design. However, Ogundele (3) found positive relationship between health workers knowledge and attitude. Our study could not find significant difference in the Interns' disposition to CPR between male and female genders. This is similar to other studies (3)(4)(5).

Our study indicated that interns with previous training during their undergraduate training scored significantly higher in knowledge ($p=0.001$), attitude ($p < 0.001$) and skill ($p < 0.001$) than those that do not have previous knowledge. This is similar to report of some authors (17). However, a study (16) found that being certified in life support courses was not associated with a higher level of knowledge. This could however be affected by period of certification to the time the study was conducted.

Comparison of performance of the respondents among the department showed that nursing interns have highest score in knowledge, attitude and skill of CPR. This probably is due to nature of work, probably because nurses encounter more victims, exposed to training as part of their in-house routine.

CONCLUSION

CPR is a vital tool in hospital and out of hospital practice for prevention of sudden death, worsening of conditions of death, and promotion of recovery. Interns are medical graduates transitioning towards independent practice. Our study showed that the Interns have a great attitude and decent knowledge in CPR. Their practical skills however, need improvement. We highly recommended that medical programs include more frequent, mandatory "hands-on" CPR simulation drills, especially for Interns in non-nursing departments.

- **Limitation**

The study depends on the self-reported scores of our respondent, which some responses may not be true reflection of their reality. Also studying larger population probably could give more valid result compared to the population of our study. Some of the departments studied contain far fewer numbers compare to the others. This may have biased the result.

REFERENCES

1. American Association. American Heart Association guidelines for cardiopulmonary resuscitation. *Emerg Cardiovasc care*, Elvister. 2016;9(2):4:1-5.
2. Perkins GD, Travers AH, Berg RA, Castren M, Considine JER et al. Adult basic life support and automated external defibrillation. 2015 *Int Consens Cardiopulm Resusc Emerg c a rdiova s cul a r c a r e s c i e n c e w i t h t r e a t m e n t R e c o m m C i r c*. 2015;132(16):51–83.
3. Nolan JP, Maconochie I, Soar J, Olasveengen TM, Greif R, Wyckoff MH et al. Executive summary. *Int Consens Cardiopulm Resusc Emerg c a rdiova s cul a r c a r e s c i e n c e w i t h t r e a t m e n t R e c o m m C i r c*. 2020;142(16):2–57.
4. Saleem M, Sheikh MA, Khan MA, Islam H, Syed R, Khan M. Empowering Tomorrow's Healers : Assessing Knowledge and Attitude Regarding CPR Training among Final-Year Doctor of Physical Therapy Students in Karachi-Cross Sectional Study. 2023;(5):782–6.
5. Okwuikpo MI, Oke M, Lesli TA, Ihunanya OM. Knowledge , Attitude and Practice of Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Among Nurses in Babcock University Teaching Hospital in. 2020;13(3):1773–82.
6. alqahtani, N.T E. assessment of basic life support(BLS) knowledge and awareness among teachers in Al-kharj city, saudi arabia. *Int J Health Sci (Qassim)*. 2023;7(1):3038–49.
7. Chew KS YM. The willingness of final year medical and dental students to perform bystander cardiopulmonary resuscitation in an Asian community. *Int J Emerg Med*. 2008;1(4):301–9.
8. Larsen MP, Eisenberg MS, Cummins RO HA. Predicting survival from out-of-hospital cardiac arrest: a graphic model. *Ann Emerg Med*. 1993;22:1652–8.
9. S. Sachdeva. A study to assess knowledge and practice of basic life support among nurses working in tertiary care hospital, New Delhi, India. *Nurs Care Open Access J*. 2020;7(2):48–52.
10. Roth GA, Johnson CO, Addolorato G, Baddour LM et al. Global burden of cardiovascular disease and risk factors. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2020;76(25):2982–3021.
11. Royal, Decree. healthcare profession practice bylaw. Available from: <https://laws.boe.gov.sa/BoeLaws/Laws/LawDetails/flde206c-eeef4-4a76-904aa9a700f2899a/1>
12. Ikechukwu Anthony KANU, PhD; Ejikemeuwa J. O. NDUBISI, PhD; Ngozi Dora ULOGU, PhD; Winifred Mary ECHE PFOE. THE “JAPA” SYNDROME AND ITS TOLL ON THE HEALTH SECTOR: A THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF THE DAILY TRUST AND VANGUARD NEWSPAPERS’ REPORTAGE OF THE MIGRATION OF HEALTH WORKERS IN NIGERIA. *African Heritage, Identity Sustain Navig Glob Post-Colonial Realities Proc 2024 Int Conf APAS*. 2024;
13. OGUNDELE, IYABODE GRACE AND OKAFOR N. Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Skills of Health Care Workers On Cardio-Pulmonary Resuscitation in Ibadan Oyo State, Nigeria. *Euro Afro Stud Int J*. 2020;1(4):28–43.
14. Dheeraj Kumar Mahendra Singh^{2*}, Manoj Kumar bharti¹ GS. Singh, Assessment of Basic Life Support Knowledge among Allied Health Professionals: A Cross-Sectional Study in

- India. *Int J Med Sci Clin Res Rev Online*. 2024;363–9.
15. Khan JA, Ur S, Khan R. Adult Basic Life Support : Update from the Recent Guidelines on Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation. 2012;51(4):143–9.
 16. Abualfraj A, Halawani A, Alshehri A, Hakim R, Hamam A. An evidence-based assessment of CPR knowledge among healthcare providers in Saudi Arabia. 2022;3(November 2021):63–74.
 17. queenth NK, teresa AE, ogban EO, bassey EN roseline A et al. basic life support skill training among health care workers in Nigeria:a state-wide evualtion in the niger-delta region. *orient j med*. 2023;35:1–2.
 18. Yamane, Yaro T. *statistics: introductory analysis*. harper row. 1967;2nd edition.